

**EFFECT OF REVERSE LOGISTICS ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF SUGAR
FACTORIES IN WESTERN KENYA SUGAR ZONE.**

ABSTRACT

Reverse logistics is becoming one of the most discussed topics among enterprises in recent times. This is due to the environmental, sustainability and climatic concerns and the fact that businesses contribute significantly to the pollution of the environment. Governments, local firms and international bodies are gradually including environmental considerations in their purchasing processes. The erratic rain patterns, the deterioration of the environmental quality, increase of infectious diseases and the issue of natural resource scarcity has forced organizations to seek affordable, durable and more so green logistical solutions. However, the third world countries have been slow in taking up such green initiatives. The purpose of this study was to determine how reverse logistics affects the financial performance of sugar factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone. This study adopted a descriptive research design. This study targeted 3004 employees in the sugar companies in western Kenya. Yamane 1967 formula was used to derive a sample size of 353 respondents for the study. The researcher adopted the use of questionnaires as the primary data collection technique. The data was analyzed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS). The study also concluded that streamlining the company functions in terms of reverse logistics helps to eliminate and cut unnecessary costs thereby improving the financial performance of the sugar company.

KEY WORDS

Material re-use, recycling, disposal of wastes, reverse logistics, financial performance

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1.1 INTRODUCTION

The changing environment and the deterioration of the natural resources have triggered organizations to identify, understand and manage the issues of environmental sustainability. This change has led to new paradigms in supply chain management strategies which have shifted the attention towards the impact to the natural environment. This shift in the supply chain management has evoked due to the growing social, political and legislative pressures (Meera, 2014).

Business organizations are considered to be the source of most of the environmental problems. They are subjected to pressures and scrutiny from various parties inside and outside the country to produce environmentally friendly products (Brammer, 2011; Eltayeb, 2010). Worldwide industrialization has led to the destruction of the environment which has resulted in unsustainable production and consumption patterns (Peprah, 2016). Industrial wastes severely damage, pollute the environment and cause ozone depletion.

Conservation issues have triggered the manufacturers on their substantial developments and production responsibilities towards a sustainable environment for all (Meera, 2014). Consumers are becoming more attuned to and involved in the growing green interests (European Commission, 2016) and customer loyalty is shifting towards environmentally friendly products. Consequently, businesses are increasingly trying to make their supply chains greener by introducing sustainability strategies throughout their organizations and supplier networks (Tukker, 2008).

According to Daugherty et al, (2001), the world of logistics has considerably changed due to globalization, modern information technology, and especially increasing ecological awareness. Large supply chain management systems are changing to global logistic networks. Awareness of the art and science of logistics continues to increase due to the increasing need for competitive advantage.

1.2 Statement of the problem

The sugar processing industry in Kenya faces the challenge of environmental sustainability and resource scarcity. The challenge of high prices of sugar and the ban on the use of plastic bags persists. The raw material scarcity problem got worse with the establishment of the companies in close proximity. Kenya's sugar production is expensive compared to the costs in the region and also internationally. In 2004, Sugar prices needed to be dropped by 39% to be in line with Common

Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) levels (Kenya Sugar Industry Strategic Plan 2010-2014). The wastes and by-products from the sugar processing pose serious concerns to the health of individuals and the environment. Air pollution occurs from the bagasse-fired boilers, sugar drying and packing. The filter mud from the production process is also dumped in the open air endangering the health of the surrounding communities. The disposal of non-bio-degradable matter is also of concern. Kipkorir (2015) and Nderitu (2014) suggest that most organizations in Kenya have not fully adopted green practices in their operations. The sugar industry faces pollution, increased operating costs, resource scarcity and increased competition. This research therefore was conducted to determine the effects of reverse logistics on the financial performance of sugar factories in western Kenya sugar Zone.

1.3 Research Objective

To determine how reverse logistics affects the financial performance of sugar factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone.

1.4 Research Hypothesis

Reverse logistics has no significant effect on the financial performance of sugar factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone.

2.1 Theoretical review

This study was guided by sustainability theory. Sustainability is meeting the needs of the current generations without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet theirs (Nawire, 2014). The theory seeks to promote appropriate development in order to do away with poverty at the same time preserve the ecological landscape. Sustainability works to understand the connections between environment, company and society. The pursuit for sustainability implies that the goal is to maintain or improve beneficial conditions, particularly with improved capacity to extend desirable conditions over the long term.

The pursuit of sustainability is oriented towards long-term treatment of natural resources, social systems in ways that are consistent with human well-being and dynamic system stability (Harrington, 2016). As such, to introduce the more complex, interwoven concepts of sustainability applications, key ideas have to be followed. The choice has to be made, the norm to be followed and the scale and manner of implementing to be considered. Therefore, a solution based on

economic analysis alone is less sustainable than one that incorporates economic, ecological and social understanding.

The OECDs environmental outlook highlights the need for new models of development centered on human well-being and the interface with the natural environment. Tackling environmental issues require a multi-stakeholder partnership, from community to national levels. It requires strong governance, institutional capacity, engagement and resources (OECD, 2015). Businesses impact and rely on the availability and health of natural resources. In recognizing this connection and protection of the habitats and biodiversity comes sustainability (Nawire, 2014). It is possible for companies to engage proactive behaviors on social and environmental issues while still delivering strong financial growth. Understanding the full cycle of operations is important in an environmentally sustainable manner and it involves key stages. These include assessing the surroundings, designing the facilities and operating with integrity to restore the environment. Thus, with the efforts to make profit, organizations are tasked to care for the environment and avoid being wasteful by recycling, reusing and disposing off waste properly.

2.2 Empirical Review

According to the research conducted by Sarhaye (2017) reverse logistics significantly affects the supply chain performance of an organization. Waste management reduces waste leading to a healthy and ecologically sound environment. Furthermore, there is a positive relation between reverse logistics and the performance of an organization.

The findings of a research conducted by Onyikwa (2016) show that inventory recovery which is part of reverse logistics is widely adopted. This has a positive relation with the performance on food and beverage firms in Kenya. Moreover, reverse logistics gives a firm the competitive advantage, reduction of operating costs, customer loyalty and increased customer base. The findings by Alshura (2016) emphasized on the significant impact that reverse logistics has on the firms environmental performance. The studied reverse logistics practices are product returns, material reuse, recycling and disposal of wastes. On the same wavelength, Mogeni (2017) found

an improved performance of an organization after the uptake of reverse logistics. This resulted in backward distribution management, lead time management and increased product returns by saving on energy, material use and overall inventory cost. It also increased customer loyalty and improved the end of product life cycle.

According to the study by Szmelter (2016) reverse logistics is applicable in food sector. The research comes up with a possibility of reverse logistics in the sugar industry. The wastes produced include beep pulp, sludge from washing and cleaning, calcium carbonate and sugar chalk. From the wastes, fertilizer can be produced. This would in turn lead to the firms making savings and improve their financial performance. The study conducted by Toke (2010) established that reverse logistics increases the rate of returns for purposes of asset recovery. It decreases the costs at reduced prices and develops a firms market for promoting green products.

Amemba (2013) found out that reverse logistics can also promote efficiency and synergy among business partners. It helps in enhancing environmental performance and reduces wastes to achieve cost savings. Moreover, reverse logistics also enhances a firm's competitiveness through enforcing efficiency and synergy among business partners, helps to enhance environmental performance and reduces waste to achieve cost savings. Chien (2007) found out that reverse logistics has a positive relationship with environmental performance of corporations. Reverse logistics has a positive relationship with financial performance. The implementation of reverse logistics can provide benefits to organizations including cost reduction, market share growth and profit increase whose effects on the financial performance of the firm are positive.

Kushwaha (2015) concluded that green initiatives such as reverse logistics have direct relationship with financial performance of a firm. Reverse logistics has a strong relationship with sustainable development. A firm that does little or no reverse logistics has no contribution to sustainable

development. The research argues that reverse logistics is one of the most important factors, not only for sustainable development but also for the firm's performance. Kamarulzaman (2014) established that many firms practice reverse logistics without familiarization with the term. The application of reverse is partial. Major practices include inventory management, product taken back and waste management. Firms that employ reverse logistics benefit in terms of quality management, reduction on the rate of goods returned and better waste management.

3.0 Research Methodology

The area expounds on the research design, population, sampling methodology, data collection procedures and instruments, pilot test, data processing and analysis.

3.1 Research Design

According to Kumar (2011), a research design is a plan, structure and strategy of investigation so conceived as to achieve certain answers to research questions or problems. It is how a research study is to be completed. The research design provides a framework for the collection and analysis of data and subsequently indicates which research methods are appropriate (Walliman, 2011).

This study adopted a descriptive research design. This is because it obtains information concerning the current status of the phenomenon with respect to the variables in this situation. Both quantitative and qualitative approaches were used because qualitative approaches are concerned with subjective assessment of attitudes, opinions and behavior (Kipkorir, 2015).

3.2 Target Population

A population is all the people or items that one wishes to carry a study on (Rahi, 2017). The target population of this study was the employees of sugar factories in western Kenya sugar zone. This study targeted 3004 employees in the sugar factories in western Kenya.

3.3 Sampling Frame

A sampling frame is a list identifying all individuals in the study population from which a research sample was selected (Kumar, 2011). The employees in the companies under investigation were clustered per company.

Table 3.1: Sampling Frame

Company	Respondents	Percentage
WESCOL	381	12.683
BSC	358	11.917
NSC	1041	36.653
MSC	1224	40.745
TOTAL	3004	100

3.4 Sample and Sampling Technique

Sampling draws inferences about the group from which the researcher selects the sample; it is a process of selecting a few (sample) from the population to become the basis for estimating or predicting the prevalence of an unknown piece of information, situation or outcome regarding the bigger group. A representative 353 officers from the four companies was selected using probability proportional size randomly sampled to participate in the study. These were the staff in the sugar factories in western Kenya.

Yamane's (1967) formula was used to determine the sample size. For a 95% confidence level and $e = 0.05$, size of the sample should be is determined by the formula below.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

In the above formula, n is the sample size, N is the accessible population size and e is the level of precision. Accordingly, the sample size is shown below.

$$n = 1 \frac{3004}{1+3004(0.05)^2} = 353$$

Therefore, the sample size for the study was 353 respondents.

3.5 Research Instruments

The researcher used questionnaires as the primary data collection method. The questionnaire was used based on some studies that have used them (Eltayeb, 2009; Namusonge, 2016). Also, questionnaires are very practical and large amount of information can be collected from a large number of people in a short period of time and in a relatively cost effective way (Kipkorir, 2015). Data was collected primarily using questionnaires which the researcher will administer personally to the target population. The data was obtained from employees of sugar factories in western Kenya sugar zone. Permission was sought from the companies and an introduction letter handed in to the management of the companies for permission to carry out the study.

3.6 Data Processing and Analysis

Data from the filled questionnaires was checked, cleaned, and examined for comprehensibility and completeness. It will then be coded, summarized and tabulated. Correlation analysis was used to determine the degree of relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variables. A five point likert scale was used to measure all the variables in this study with the following codes, 1 (strongly disagree) 2 (disagree) 3 (neutral) 4 (agree) and (strongly agree).

A likert scale is based upon the assumption that each statement on the scale has equal attitudinal value, importance or weight (Kumar, 2011). Data collected was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software where selected variables were subjected to statistical analysis (Ramakrishnan, 2015).

4.0 Data analysis

The data collected from the field was coded, summarized, analysed, and tabulated.

4.1 Response Rate

The researcher administered questionnaires to 353 respondents who were sampled out as the targeted population in chapter three above. 318 duly filled questionnaires were returned. This represents a response rate of 90.08 %. According to Baruch and Holtom, (2008), the average level

of response of 52.7% is considered acceptable for sampling. Thus, the response rate achieved in this study can be considered sufficient to give the findings adequate reliability.

4.2 Reverse Logistics

The study sought to determine the respondent’s level of agreement with effect of reverse logistics on the performance of sugar companies. Table 4.1 shows the findings.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Reverse Logistics

Reverse Logistics Statement	1	2	3	4	5	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std
	SD	D	U	A	SA					Dev
Our company procures products that are made using recycled materials	0.0	2.7	18.0	36.1	43.2	353	2	5	4.20	.829
The company recycles wastes from the production	0.0	2.7	7.2	45.9	44.2	353	2	5	4.32	.726
The company re-uses by-products for other purposes	0.0	0.0	11.7	41.5	46.8	353	3	5	4.35	.683
There is the implementation of the waste to energy process	0.9	0.9	8.2	44.1	45.9	353	1	5	4.33	.743
Waste reduction has led to better economic performance of the sugar company	0.0	0.9	7.2	45.1	46.8	353	2	5	4.38	.661
The practices of waste reduction/reuse/re-cycling have led to efficiency in the company	0.0	1.8	5.4	47.8	45.0	353	2	5	4.36	.671
The practices of waste reduction/reuse/re-cycling have led to better quality of products in the company	0.0	0.9	7.2	47.8	44.1	353	2	5	4.35	.656
The practices of waste reduction/reuse/re-cycling have led to cost reduction in the company operations	0.0	1.8	6.3	50.5	41.4	353	2	5	4.32	.674
Grand Mean = 4.326										
Valid N (Listwise) = 353										

4.3 Effect of organization reverse logistics on financial performance

The correlation analysis results of the effect of Reverse Logistics on organizational performance of the sugar processing companies in Western Kenya sugar zones was presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Reverse Logistics

	Organizational Performance
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Reverse Logistics	Pearson Correlation	.842 ^{**}
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The study showed that there was a positively statistically significant effect of reverse logistics on organizational performance ($r = 0.842$; $p < 0.05$). This meant that reverse logistics has a direct influence on organizational performance of the sugar processing companies in Western Kenya sugar zones. The findings of this corroborated the study conducted by Toke (2010) which established that reverse logistics increases the rate of returns for purposes of asset recovery. It decreases the costs at reduced prices and develops a firms market for promoting green products.

4.4 Simple Linear Regression Analysis

The study established an effect of reverse logistics on financial performance. The results of multiple regression analysis shown in Table 4.16 **Table 4.3: Simple Linear Regression Model Summary**

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate
.898 ^a	.806	.779	.337

a. Predictors: (Constant), Reverse Logistics

b. Dependent Variable: Financial performance

From table 4.3, R-Squared is used to evaluate the goodness of fit of a model. In regression, the R square coefficient of determination is a statistical measure of how well the regression line approximates the real data. It measures the proportion of the variation in dependent variable explained by independent variables. From the results on model summary $R = 0.898$, $R\text{-square} = 0.806$, $\text{adjusted } R\text{-square} = 0.779$, and the $SE = 0.337$. The coefficient of determination also called the R square is 0.806. This implies that the effect of the predictor variable (Reverse logistics) explains 80.6% of the variations in financial performance of sugar factories. This implies that a change in reverse logistics has a strong and a positive effect on financial performance of sugar

factories. This study thus assumes that the difference of 19.4% of the variations is as a result of other factors.

5.1 Results and Discussion

The objective of the study sought to determine how reverse logistics affect the financial performance of sugar factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone. The study indicated that reverse logistics is positively and significantly related with financial performance sugar factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone. This implied that a reverse logistics is a critical factor for financial performance of sugar factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone. These findings meant that the null hypothesis that Reverse logistics has no significant effect on the financial performance of sugar factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone was rejected.

5.2 Conclusions

From the findings of the study, it was concluded that reverse logistics was a predictor for financial performance. The study also concluded that streamlining the company functions in terms of reverse logistics helps to eliminate and cut unnecessary costs thereby improving the financial performance of the sugar company.

5.3 Recommendations on policy formulation and practice

Based on the results, findings and conclusions, the study recommended that the management of factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone should stop taking for granted the reverse logistics processes and initiatives. From the farmers' words, the management of the various sugar factories has failed in proper implementation of such logistics and in most cases such processes have been seen as backward and of immaterial value to the organizations. It is therefore a recommendation that such green practices should be put into full implementation in order to not only make the farmers happy but also to improve on the financial performance of such sugar factories.

To the academia and researchers, this study just opened up a new area that indeed needs to be looked at intensively since. Since the study only looked at factories in Western Kenya Sugar Zone, more scholars should come up and try to see if the application of these findings could be replicated with the other sugar manufacturing companies across the globe and even to the privately owned sugar firms.

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